

Data Management Plan

World Development Visualization Dashboard

Grant number 1

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Based on Common DSW Knowledge Model, 2.0.1 (dsw:root:2.0.1)

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Data Management Plan created in Data Stewardship Wizard <<https://ds-wizard.org>>

Abstract

The project consists of analyzing a dataset using visual and statistical means in order to discover/find insights in it and then building an interactive visualization dashboard that can be used to analyze the discovered insights.

The dataset is a combination of multiple datasets from Gapminder, representing development indicators about (almost) all countries around the world over the last two centuries.

Section A: Data Collection

1. What data will you collect or create?

Re-used datasets We will use the following reference datasets:

- **Gapminder World** (<https://zenodo.org/record/1039839>)
The data is publically available at: <https://www.gapminder.org/data/>
(accessed 20.04.2020)

Data formats and types We will be using the following data formats and types:

- **CSV Dialect Description Format**

It is a standardized format. This is a suitable format for long-term archiving.
We will have only a small amount of data stored in this format.

2. How will the data be collected or created?

There will be no instrument dataset in this project.

Storage and file conventions We will use a filesystem with files and folders.
We have made appointments about naming the files.

We will not be storing data in an "object store" system.

We will not use a relational database system to store project data.

We will not use a graph database for data in the project.

We will not be storing data in a triple store.

Section B: Documentation and Meta-data

3. What documentation and meta-data will accompany the data?

List of data to be published is given in Section E, Question 9. This also includes information about catalogs where the data can be found. Information about data types used is given in Section A, Question 1.

We will use an electronic lab notebook to make sure that there is good provenance of the data analysis.

Section C: Ethics and Legal Compliance

4. How will you manage any ethical issues?

The used data does not require any protection since it's freely available online and does not include any personal or sensitive information.

5. How will you manage copyright and Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) issues?

We will be working with the philosophy *as open as possible* for our data.

All of our data can become completely open immediately.

For the reference and non-reference data sets that we reuse, conditions are as follows:

- **Gapminder World** – freely available with obligation to quote the source (e.g. CC-BY).

Section D: Storage and Backup

6. How will the data be stored and backed up during the research?

The code and data will be stored in a git repository publicly accessible:

<https://github.com/GhaithArf/visualisation-dashboard/>

A local backup of the repository is available on the contributor machines.

7. How will you manage access and security?

All data centers where project data is stored carry sufficient certifications. All project web services addressed via secure http (<https://...>). Project members have been instructed about both generic and specific risks to the project.

The possible impact to the project or organization if information is lost is small. The possible impact to the project or organization if information is leaked is small. The possible impact to the project or organization if information is vandalised is small.

We are not using any personal information.

Section E: Selection and Preservation

8. Which data are of long-term value and should be retained, shared, and/or preserved?

We plan to publish the following datasets:

- **Gapminder World subset merged** – This data set will be kept available as long as technically possible. – The metadata will be available even when the data no longer exists.

9. What is the longterm preservation plan for the dataset?

- **Gapminder World subset merged** will be stored in a domain-specific repository: GitHub.

It is available under the following link: <https://github.com/GhaithArf/visualisation-dashboard/tree/master/data/merged>

We don't need to contact the repository because it is a routine for us. We will be adding a reference to the published data to at least one data catalogue.

None of the used repositories charge for their services.

We have a reserved budget for the time and effort it will take to prepare the data for publication.

Section F: Data Sharing

10. How will you share the data?

- **Gapminder World subset merged** – freely available for any use (public domain or CC0).

The DOI of the produced dataset is:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3757329>

Information about used repositories (i.e. where will potential users find out about the data) is provided in Section E, Question 9.

Embargo on the data is described in Section C, Question 5, and Section F, Question 11.

11. Are any restrictions on data sharing required?

Ethical and legal restrictions are documented under Section C. We have used the Data Stewardship Wizard, which made us aware of options to minimize the restrictions.

No data sharing agreement will be required.

Section G: Responsibilities and Resources

12. Who will be responsible for data management?

Ghaith Arfaoui is responsible for implementing the DMP, and ensuring it is reviewed and revised.

Ghaith Arfaoui is responsible for reviewing, enhancing, cleaning, or standardizing metadata and the associated data submitted for storage, use and maintenance within a data centre or repository.

13. What resources will you require to deliver your plan?

To execute the DMP, no additional specialist expertise is required.

We do not require any hardware or software in addition to what is usually available in the institute.

Charges applied by data repositories (if any) are mentioned already in Section E, Question 9.